

Study on Laser Drilling in PWB (Small Diameter Drilling in GFRP)

Hisahiro INOUE, Faculty of Eng., Univ. of Osaka Pref. , Osaka 590, Japan.

Eiichi AOYAMA, Faculty of Eng., Doshisha Univ., Kyoto 610-03, Japan.

Toshiki HIROGAKI, Osaka Pref. Industrial Technology Research Institute, Osaka 590, Japan.

Hiromichi NOBE, Graduate Student, Doshisha Univ., Kyoto 610-03, Japan.

Youji KITAHARA, Osaka Pref. Industrial Technology Research Institute, Osaka 590, Japan.

Tsutaio KATAYAMA, Faculty of Eng., Doshisha Univ. , Kyoto 610-03, Japan.

ABSTRACT

This paper describes characteristics of the small diameter drilling in GFRP using laser beam machines in order to devise the non-traditional process of drilling in printed wiring board(PWB) as no contact machining. Drilling is performed by a CO₂ laser machine and a YAG laser machine. The damages of drilled holes are examined in order to investigate a laser drilling process of GFRP, and the drilling factors(output power, irradiation time, wavelength) are varied in order to assess the effect on damages. From these results, it is shown that the application of a CO₂ laser source is effective on smaller diameter drilling in GFRP for PWB.

INTRODUCTION

It has been required that the production of printed wiring board(PWB) is not only increasing in quantity but also improving in quality. Among others, it has been required that the packaging density of PWB is improved. High packaging density technology has realized to downsize. For instance, from a general public point of view, the televisions and telephones are typical cases of downsizing, so that their use has changed from stationary to portable. From an industrial point of view, the computing speed and the memory size are increasing. Thus, high-quality micro-machinings are necessary for PWB. Specially, the small diameter drilling in PWB has been paid attention, because the packaging density must be improved. On the other hand, a great number of holes in PWB have to be drilled and drilled holes are required the reliability for through-hole plating. Even if the only one hole in the production is failed to be drilled, this whole production has to be abandoned. Consequently, in order to improve the reliability of smaller diameter drilling in PWB, it is necessary that the non-traditional drilling process without the concern of tool life is researched because it is difficult to predict the tool life in drilling of the traditional drilling machine.

Hitherto, there are a few studies[1]-[3] which are dealt with drilling in FRP by the drilling machine. However, there are very few studies[4] which are dealt with laser drilling in FRP. In particular, there is no study that is dealt with small diameter drilling for through-hole plating on PWB, made of GFRP, using a laser machine.

So, this paper describes characteristics of the small diameter drilling in GFRP in order to construct the non-traditional drilling process of PWB.

First, the laser drilling in GFRP using a CO₂ source (wavelength 10.6 μm) is performed, because both the resins and glass fibers in GFRP are expected to be machined efficiently due to the absorption of a CO₂ laser beam. Recently, CO₂ laser drilling machines have been just utilized for machining the organic compound PWB. In order to investigate a laser drilling process, the damage of drilled hole in the cross sections is examined by optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM), and the drilled PWB, whose resin is vaporized in a furnace at 600°C after drilling, is observed by microscope. The output power of laser and laser irradiation time are varied to examine the effect on the damage.

Secondly, the laser drilling in GFRP using a YAG source (wavelength 1.06 μm) is performed, because a YAG laser has been promising in the micro-machining and has been utilized practically for marking, trimming, scribing and welding in the micro-machining fields. These experimental results of a YAG laser are compared with those of a CO₂ laser.

EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

The maximum attainable power of this CO₂ laser is 250 W and that of this YAG laser is 300 W. Spot diameter is 0.3 mm, and the focus length is 127 mm. Assisting gas used in laser drilling is N₂ or air. This GFRP is the type of glass (39% in mass)/epoxy-resin, plain woven cloth and thickness 1.6 mm. The workpiece is the copper clad laminate for PWB.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CO₂ LASER DRILLING

The Damages in CO₂ Laser Drilling

The laser beam machining is effective on the material which has the high absorption and the low thermal conductivity. Both the epoxy resin and the glass, which GFRP is made of, are the absorbent materials on a CO₂ laser beam, and these thermal conductivity are lower than the steel's one.

Fig. 1 shows the microscope photograph of the drilled epoxy resin using a CO₂ laser. Fig. 2 shows the microscope photograph of the drilled glass cloth using a CO₂ laser. It is shown in Fig. 1 that the thermal decomposition (pyrolysis) and the complete combustion of the epoxy resin are carried out by a CO₂ laser in a moment and the heat affected damage is hardly appeared at the drilled hole wall. On the other hand, it is shown in Fig. 2 that the melted zone is appeared at the drilled hole wall of the glass cloth and that drilling the glass fibers is more difficult than drilling the epoxy resin with a CO₂ laser machine. This is the reason the melting point of the glass is very higher than that of epoxy resin.

Fig. 3 shows the microscope photograph of the drilled GFRP using a CO₂ laser. It is observed in Fig. 3 that the heat affected black damage, which cannot be observed in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, exists at the drilled hole wall. Fig. 4 shows the SEM photograph of the same drilled GFRP in Fig. 3. Fig. 5 shows the high magnification SEM photograph of Fig. 4. It is observed in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 that

there is no glass fiber near the hole wall and glass fiber, on which the pyrolytic carbon deposits, far from the hole wall in the damage zone (black part in Fig.3).

Figure 1. The microscope photograph of the drilled epoxy resin using a CO₂ laser (Laser output power 35 W, Irradiation time 0.1 s, Around the air)

Figure 2. The microscope photograph of the drilled glass cloth using a CO₂ laser (Laser output power 75 W, Irradiation time 0.1 s, Assisting gas N₂)

Figure 3. The microscope photograph of the drilled GFRP using a CO₂ laser (Laser output power 75 W, Irradiation time 0.1 s, Assisting gas N₂)

Fig.6(a) shows the microscope photograph of the hole entrance side of GFRP, and Fig.6(b) shows the glass cloth in GFRP whose resin is vaporized at 600°C. This damage is hardly dependent on the fiber direction, because we can see circle damage zone in Fig.6(a). By comparison Fig.6(a) with Fig.6(b), the black substance in the heat affected damage is separated into the carbon

(vaporization at 600 °C) and graphite, etc. (no vaporization). In detail, the epoxy resin (low resolution point) is decomposed by the thermal conduction, and then the pyrolytic carbon deposits on the glass fibers. So, the surface of the glass fibers turns to black. Further, the temperature of the glass fibers near the hole wall rises to melting point, while the carbon on the glass fibers varies to the graphite and SiC. In other words, in the damage, the temperature of the fiber residual part is higher than that of the resin decomposition and is lower than that of the glass melting (about 500-1500 °C), and that of no fiber part is higher than that of the glass melting and is lower than that of the graphite decomposition (about 1500-3500 °C). Moreover, the vapor pressure in the melted material at the center of the hole becomes higher, because the energy density is higher at the center of a laser beam. So, the material flows from the center (high pressure) to the hole wall (low pressure), and flows to the hole entrance along the wall, as shown in Fig.7 which indicates the state of the drilling a hole using CO₂ laser. The glass fibers are bent to the hole entrance side as shown in Fig.5.

Figure 4. SEM photograph of the drilled GFRP using a CO₂ laser (Laser output power 75 W, Irradiation time 0.1 s, Assisting gas N₂)

Figure 5. High magnification SEM photograph of the drilled hole wall using a CO₂ laser (GFRP, Laser output power 75 W, Irradiation time 0.1 s, Assisting gas N₂)

Figure 6. The microscope photograph of the hole entrance side by a CO₂ laser drilling (laser output power 150 W, Irradiation time 0.5 s, Assisting gas N₂)

Figure 7. Schematic profile of drilled hole

The Drilling Condition and The Damage

Fig. 8 shows the relation between the diameters of the heat affected black damage and laser output powers in cases of irradiation time 0.1 s and 0.5 s. Fig. 9 (a) and (b) show the relation between the width of the whole damage and no glass zone in the damage (illustrated in Fig. 7) and the laser irradiation time in case of 150W and 75W in output power, respectively.

It is indicated in Fig. 8 that the heat affected diameter is increasing, as the laser output power is increasing. On the other hand, from Fig. 9 (a) and (b), the damage width from the hole wall is the same at the each laser output power approximately. That is; in Fig. 8, the spot diameter is the same at each output power, but the laser power density is different at the same diameter. So, the drilled diameter is increasing, as the laser output power is increasing. From Fig. 9, the width of damage is not related to laser output power but to irradiation time, because the temperature is the same at the drilled hole wall and the heat affected zone occurs due to the heat conduction from drilled hole wall. In other words, the laser irradiation time is more important factor than the output power of laser. In order to reduce the damage zone, it is effective to decrease the laser irradiation time in drilling.

Figure 8. The diameter of the heat affected black damage and the output power of a CO₂ laser (Irradiation time 0.1 s, 0.5 s, Assisting gas N₂, the hole entrance side)

Figure 9. The damage width and irradiation time (the hole entrance side, Assisting gas N₂)

YAG LASER DRILLING

In the practical laser machines, a YAG source is expected to be a high efficient, because it can accomplish the maximum power about 10-2000W and excels at emitting a pulse of laser. Fig.10 and Fig.11 (high magnification) show the SEM photographs of the drilled hole using a YAG laser. On the other hand, Fig.12 shows the microscope photograph of the drilled hole using a YAG laser at the cross section. It is found in Fig.10 that drilling in GFRP is possible and that the damage zone is reduced by decreasing a laser irradiation time. In Fig.11, the damage around the hole is similar to that of drilling using CO₂ laser, and its width reduces up to about 0.05 mm. From Fig.12, the anisotropic damage zone is observed along the fibers. This is the reason the epoxy resin absorbs most of the YAG laser beam and the glass doesn't due to the wave length of YAG. So, some of YAG laser light which is transmitted in glass fibers affects the matrix (epoxy resin) along the fiber widely.

Figure 10. SEM photograph of the drilled hole using a YAG laser (1.7 J/pulse, 2.5ms/pulse, 7pulses)

Figure 11. High magnification SEM photograph of the drilled hole using a YAG laser (1.7 J/pulse, 2.5ms/pulse, 7pulses)

Figure 12. The microscope photograph of the drilled hole using a YAG laser (1.7 J/pulse, 5.0ms/pulse, 5pulses)

SUMMARY

1. The heat affected black damage, which cannot be observed in epoxy resin and glass fibers, exists at the drilled hole wall of GFRP by a CO₂ laser machine. The damage area is separated into the glass/carbon and graphite/SiC due to temperatures distribution in drilling.

2. It is important to decrease the laser irradiation time in order to reduce the damage area in laser drilling.
3. In the case of a YAG laser drilling, the heat affected area around the hole is similar to that of a CO₂ laser. However, some of YAG laser light transmitted in glass fibers damages the matrix (epoxy resin) along the fiber widely.
4. By comparing a CO₂ laser drilling with a YAG laser drilling, it is indicated that the application of a CO₂ laser source is effective in the smaller diameter drilling in PWB made of GFRP as a non-traditional process of no contact machining.

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